

1 **Transparent antibiofouling coating to improve the efficiency of *Nannochloropsis***
2 ***gaditana* and *Chlorella sorokiniana* culture photobioreactors at the pilot-plant scale**

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23 **Abstract**

24 The implementation of industrial-scale facilities for microalgae cultivation is limited
25 due to the high operation costs. One of the main problems in obtaining an efficient and
26 long-lasting microalgae culture system is biofouling. The particular issue when
27 developing antibiofouling surfaces for microalgae cultures is that the material must be
28 transparent. The main purpose of this work was to evaluate the antibiofouling efficiency
29 of a non-toxic polydimethylsiloxane-based coating prepared with polyethylene glycol-
30 based copolymer on different photobioreactors at the pilot-plant scale. The antifouling
31 properties result from the development of a fouling-release coating utilizing hydrogel
32 technology. *Nannochloropsis gaditana* and *Chlorella sorokiniana* were cultured
33 outdoors for 3 months over the summer, when biofouling formation is at its highest due
34 to environmental conditions, to test the coating's antibiofouling efficiency. Although
35 biofouling was not completely prevented in either photobioreactor, the coating
36 significantly reduced cell adhesion compared to the polydimethylsiloxane control (70%
37 less adhesion). Therefore, this coating was shown to be a good alternative for
38 constructing efficient closed-photobioreactors at the pilot-plant scale, at least for
39 cultures lasting 3 months.

40 **Keywords**

41 Flat-panel, tubular photobioreactor, biofouling, amphiphilic surface, fouling-release
42 coatings

43 **1. Introduction**

44 In recent years, microalgae have received a lot of interest due to their potential as a
45 renewable fossil fuel substitute, their abundant content of high-value products and even
46 to their use for bioremediation (Chisti, 2007; Kusmayadi et al., 2021; Priya et al., 2022;
47 Yap et al., 2021). To produce large amounts of these products to satisfy the increasing

48 market demand, it is necessary to scale up the process for producing the microalgal
49 biomass. However, it is currently very difficult to achieve an economical and long-
50 lasting microalgae culture system, mainly because of biofouling formation, or cell
51 adhesion (Zerrouh et al., 2017). This is especially so in spring and summer when
52 biofouling formation is greater because of high temperature and irradiance (San Pedro et
53 al., 2016), which in many cases means that production has to be halted during these
54 months. Besides the environmental conditions, culture conditions also influence
55 microalgae cell adhesion. Soriano-Jerez et al. (2021) and García-Abad et al. (2022)
56 observed that modifying the N/P¹ ratio in *Nannochloropsis gaditana* culture, and in
57 *Chamydomonas reinhardtii* and *Isochrysis galbana*, respectively, changes the biomass
58 concentration. This, in turn, affects cell adhesion because the variation in the N/P ratio
59 influences the secretion of EPS², such as proteins and carbohydrates. As a result, an
60 increased EPS concentration in the supernatant leads to increased cell adhesion on PBR³
61 walls. Furthermore, phosphates can interact with BSA⁴ protein to form complexes, the
62 preferred structure of adsorbed BSA on surfaces (Jeyachandran et al., 2009). Although
63 it has not yet been verified whether the micronutrient concentration affects microalgae
64 cell adhesion in PBRs, it is known that these micronutrients can and do influence the
65 adhesion of bacteria and diatoms (Geesey et al., 2000; Wang et al., 2019). In those
66 studies, it was reported that divalent cations of magnesium and calcium have a huge
67 influence on cell attachment and on biofilm structural maturation due to their effect on
68 gene regulation, physicochemical interactions, and bio-macromolecular structural
69 changes. Ions, especially divalent ions, also influence membrane fouling formation
70 (Abrahamse et al., 2008; Kilmer et al., 2021). Anions and cations can interact with EPS

¹ Nitrogen to phosphorus

² Exopolymeric substances

³ Photobioreactor

⁴ Bovine serum albumin

71 by forming complexes that promote cell adhesion (Medda et al., 2015), so it is expected
72 that they also promote microalgae cell adhesion. Bacteria also have influence on
73 biofouling development in microalgae culture (Giraldo et al., 2019).
74 Problems resulting from biofouling are more significant in closed PBRs such as flat-
75 panels and tubular (Zerriouh et al., 2017). Although raceways (open PBRs) are cheaper
76 to build and operate, they are more susceptible to contamination and light availability
77 (Gupta et al., 2015); that is why, in many cases, it is necessary to work with closed
78 PBRs under outdoor conditions. Biofouling is greatly influenced by the PBR geometry
79 and the construction materials used for the walls, which are traditionally constructed of
80 glass or plastic, for example, PMMA⁵ (Gupta et al., 2015; Koller, 2015). In general,
81 flat-panel PBR designs are easier to clean and maintain than tubular PBRs because their
82 geometry is more cuboidal (Assunção & Malcata, 2020). Tubular PBRs also have
83 significant disadvantages due to their fluid rate being dependent on a pump. The curved
84 areas of the tubes are where biofouling is most likely to form. Various approaches have
85 been proposed to address this specific tubular design problem, such as introducing
86 poly(urethane) foam balls or scouring pads into the tubes (Tsygankov et al., 1998),
87 (Koller, 2015). However, these particles must be separated from the culture, making the
88 harvesting process more difficult. Another option for avoiding microalgae cell adhesion
89 on PBR walls is to cover them with antibiofouling coatings. However, the transparent
90 commercial coatings currently available do not successfully prevent microalgae
91 adhesion; only the opaque commercial paint Hempasil X3® has demonstrated minimal
92 microalgae cell adhesion in *N. gaditana*⁶, *C. reinhardtii*⁷ and *I. galbana*⁸ cultures
93 (García-Abad et al., 2022; Soriano-Jerez et al., 2021; Zerriouh et al., 2019). For this

⁵ poly(methyl methacrylate)

⁶ *Nannochloropsis gaditana*

⁷ *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*

⁸ *Isochrysis galbana*

94 reason, new transparent PEG⁹/PDMS¹⁰-based coatings aimed at preventing protein
95 adsorption have been developed to avoid microalgae cell adhesion yielding outstanding
96 outcomes due to their foundation in hydrogel technology. Upon contact with water,
97 these coatings hydrate and acquire a hydrophilic characteristic (Thorlaksen et al., 2010).
98 Water forms a protective layer over the surface, driven by a remarkably strong surface-
99 water interaction energy. As a result, when a microalga cell approaches the surface,
100 breaking this interaction becomes exceedingly challenging, making it difficult for the
101 cell to adhere to the surface. Nevertheless, to date, this type of coating has only been
102 tested indoors and in open PBRs (which are easy to paint since the surface is flat and
103 open) with cultures of the marine microalga *N. gaditana* (Soriano-Jerez et al., 2023).
104 The objective of this work is to demonstrate the antibiofouling efficiency of a
105 transparent, non-toxic PEG/PDMS coating based on hydrogel technology applied to
106 outdoor PBRs (at the pilot-plant scale), both in flat-panel PBRs, where the surfaces are
107 straight and easy to paint, and in tubular PBRs, where one is faced with the difficulty of
108 applying the coating inside the tubes. The cultures were carried out with monoalgal
109 cultures, the marine microalgae *N. gaditana* and *C. sorokiniana*¹¹, for 3 months over the
110 summer, when cell adhesion is at its greatest level due to higher average temperatures
111 and irradiance (San Pedro et al., 2016) in order, in a future, to test these coatings in
112 heterogeneous cultures from different bioremediation with microalgae uses (where the
113 biofouling formed will be higher than in monoculture ones). EPS, such as proteins and
114 carbohydrates, along with the concentration of anions and cations present in the
115 supernatant and the microbiota community, were determined to analyse their influence
116 on biofouling formation. Furthermore, the content of metals in the biomass and adhered

⁹ Polyethylene glycol

¹⁰ Poly(dimethylsiloxane)

¹¹ *Chlorella sorokiniana*

117 cells was quantified to determine if they were bioremediated by the microalgae or if
118 they attached to the surfaces by forming complexes.

119 **2. Materials and Methods**

120 2.1. Microalgal strains and culture medium

121 The marine culture collection at the Andalusian institute of marine science (CSIC)
122 proporcionated the marine microalgae *N. gaditana* B-3 and *C. sorokiniana*. 80 L bubble
123 columns were used to grow the inoculum of both strains at the pilot plant of the
124 University of Almería, Spain (+36° 49' 43.13'', - 2° 24' 9.39''). The base of the culture
125 media was Mediterranean seawater, pumped right away from the sea into a 500 L tank
126 to storage, along with fertilizers for agriculture (Camacho-Rodríguez et al., 2013b; San
127 Pedro et al., 2016): KH₂PO₄ (Agro Mayor, Fuentes Fertilizantes S.A., Spain), NaNO₃
128 (SQM Europe N.V., Belgium), and necessary micronutrients (Welgro Hidroponic,
129 Welgro, The Netherlands) using a nitrogen to phosphorus ratio (N/P) of 15 (Soriano-
130 Jerez et al., 2021). To keep the pH level at 8.0, pure CO₂ was fed, as needed, into the
131 incoming air stream.

132 2.2. Photobioreactors and culture mode

133 *N. gaditana* and *C. sorokiniana* were monoalgal non axenically cultivated in two 400 L
134 flat-panel photobioreactors, each having the same dimensions and orientation. The
135 photobioreactors were located in Almería, Spain; they were positioned facing East-West
136 (+36° 49' 43.07'', -2° 24' 8.93''). Each reactor was made of a single-use plastic bag
137 (TRC premium DH, Sotrafa, Almería, Spain) placed between two steel frames spaced at
138 an average distance of 0.08 m. The steel structure and plastic bag were 2.5 m long and
139 1.7 m high. The transparency index of the plastic bag in the photosynthetically active
140 spectrum was 0.95 and was manufactured of 0.75 µm free-dispersant polyethylene. At
141 the bottom of the photobioreactor, a gas sparger was placed to supply aeration at a 0.09

142 v/v/min flow rate (FR4L72BVBN flowmeters, Key Instruments, USA). When
143 necessary, CO₂ was fed at 0.01 v/v/min rate (FR4A41BVBN flow meters, Key
144 Instruments, USA) to maintain the pH at 8.0 (San Pedro et al., 2016).

145 *N. gaditana* and *C. sorokiniana* were also cultivated non axenically in two different
146 closed PMMA tubular PBRs, as previously described (Molina et al., 2001; San Pedro et
147 al., 2014). Briefly, the working volume of each tubular PBR was 340 L. Each comprised
148 a vertical tubular solar receiver measuring 120 m in length and 0.05 m in diameter, as
149 well as a bubble column for O₂ degassing and heat exchange that was 1.92 m high and
150 0.25 m in diameter. The culture was recirculated through the reactor with the help of a
151 centrifugal pump (Kripsol, KORAL-KSE, Toledo, Spain). The pH was maintained at
152 8.0 by injecting pure CO₂ into the incoming air stream as needed in both cases. The air
153 circulation rate was 0.1 v/v/min (FR4L72BVBN flow meters, Key Instruments, USA)
154 and the 0.01 v/v/min for the CO₂ flow rate (FR4A41BVBN flow meters, Key
155 Instruments, USA) as required.

156 In all the PBRs, a low-cost, fertilizer-based, agricultural medium developed by
157 Camacho-Rodríguez et al. (2013b) was selected as basis. The phosphorus concentration
158 was altered to achieve the desired N/P ratio of 15 (Soriano-Jerez et al., 2021). The
159 experiment started, in the flat-panel PBRs, with an initial biomass concentration of 0.40
160 ± 0.01 g/L and 0.31 ± 0.01 g/L for *N. gaditana* and *C. sorokiniana*, respectively; in the
161 tubular PBRs, it was 0.39±0.01 g/L and 0.30±0.01 g/L for *N. gaditana* and *C.*
162 *sorokiniana*, respectively. The initial pH was 7.8 in all cases. When the stationary state
163 was achieved, the continuous phase of the experiment began after a batch phase. Fresh
164 medium was added at a constant velocity to maintain the required dilution rate. Flow
165 meters (FCIV0201D, 10100, FIP, Italy) were used to control the culture medium
166 volume going into the reactors controlled by. At the top of the culture, the medium inlet

167 was placed in the middle of the reactor. The reactors were in used for 3 months (from
168 July to October 2022). In all the PBRs, the temperature was kept below 30°C by
169 circulating tap water through a heat exchanger.

170 2.3. Preparation of the antibiofouling coatings

171 In accordance with Soriano-Jerez et al. (2023), DBE-311 copolymer from Gelest
172 (Pennsylvania, USA) was used to prepare a fouling-release coating on a PDMS
173 elastomer matrix. This choice was made due to its high transparency, exceeding 90%
174 as previously reported (Soriano-Jerez et al., 2023) along its excellent indoor
175 antibiofouling properties. The PDMS utilized was Sylgard™ 184, provided by Dow
176 Corning (Michigan, USA). To prepare the antibiofouling coating, 4% w/w of DBE-311
177 was mixed with Sylgard 184 (PDMS oil:crosslinker 10:1 w/w), xylene (Chem-Lab,
178 Zedelgem, Belgium) was used as the solvent. To remove all the bubbles, the mixture
179 was placed in a vacuum. Then, it was applied over the surface. To apply the coatings to
180 the plastic bag with a controlled thickness of 120 µm, a micrometre-adjustable film
181 applicator (3580/3 Universal micrometre applicator, Neurtek, Spain) was used. The
182 curing reaction for the coatings applied on flat-panels walls was done at 60°C by using
183 heated air.

184 In the case of the tubular PBR, an airless Graco® coater with a 517 tip (Classic 290 PC,
185 Stand Graco, Clemco, Spain) was used to apply the coatings to the interior surface of
186 the glass tubes. The curing reaction of the tubes was carried out on a lathe so that the
187 coating was homogeneously distributed over the entire surface, using heated air (60°C)
188 to accelerate the process.

189 Sylgard™ 184 (PDMS), Hempasil X₃® (Hempel A/S, Denmark), and the untreated
190 plastic bag (TRC premium DH, Sotrafa, Almería, Spain) were used as controls in the
191 flat panel PBR, while PMMA was used as control in the case of the tubular PBR.

2.4. Physicochemical properties of the surfaces and microalgae cells

The surfaces (pristine plastic bag and pristine coatings, and plastic bag and coatings after 3 months of immersion in each microalgae culture) and microalgae cells (after lawn preparation) were characterized by measuring the water, formamide, and diiodomethane contact angle values using sessile drop technique, with a droplet volume of 5 μL , utilising a goniometer (Drop Shape Analyzer DSA25). From these measurements, the surface energy components (γ_s^{LW} , γ_s^+ , γ_s^- , γ_s^{AB}), free energy of cohesion (ΔG_{coh}), surface free energy (γ_s), water adhesion tension (τ_0), and critical surface tension (γ_c) were calculated as described previously (Zerriouh et al., 2019). A surface profiler (PCE-RT 11, PCE Ibérica S.L., Albacete, Spain) was used to measure the media surface roughness (Ra) with a 1 mm scan length and a 0.111 μm / sample resolution.

Microalgal lawns were prepared as previously described (Zerriouh et al., 2017). Briefly, concentrated culture samples were centrifuged and washed with ammonium carbonate (40 g/L). Reconstituted pellets passed through 0.45 μm cellulose acetate filters (Sartorius Stedim Biotech GmbH, Germany) before being resuspended in 5 mL of deionized water. The obtained microalgal lawns were placed on a Petri plate over 1% agar (w/v), prepared with 10% (v/v) glycerol in water for 30 min at room temperature. Subsequently, after 50 min at 26°C, the extra water was removed.

2.5. DNA extraction and 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing library preparation

To assess the microbial community in the tubular-PBR culture, the total genomic DNA was extracted from the collected sample using the FastDNA-2 mL SPIN kit and the FastPrep24 apparatus (MP-Bio, Santa Ana, CA, USA) as described by Maza-Márquez et al. (2017). High-throughput Illumina MiSeq sequencing was performed at the facilities of the Institute of Parasitology and Biomedicine “Lopez-Neyra”

217 (<http://www.ipb.csic.es>). The V3 and V4 variable regions of the 16S rRNA gene were
218 amplified from the bacterial DNA using the primers 16S Pro V3V4, forward (5'
219 CCTACGGGNBGCASCAG 3') and reverse (5' GACTACNVGGGTATCTAATCC
220 3'). The amplification conditions for the bacteria were: 95°C 3'; (95°C 30''; 75°C 10'';
221 55°C 30''; 72°C 30'') x 25 cycles; 72°C 5'; 4°C hold. For the Chlorophyta, the 18S
222 rRNA region was amplified using the primers Chloro-F (5'-TGG CCT ATC TTG TTG
223 GTC TGT-3') and Chloro-R (5' -GAA TCA ACC TGA CAA GGC AAC-3'). The
224 amplification conditions were: 95°C 3', 27x (95°C 30'', 59°C 30'', 72°C 30''), 72°C 5';
225 4°C hold (Maza-Márquez et al., 2017).

226 Raw sequencing data were performed using QIIME software, v. 1.9.1. (Caporaso et al.,
227 2012), as described elsewhere (Gallardo-Altamirano et al., 2021; Maza-Márquez et al.,
228 2017). Taxonomic close-reference assignments based on a 97% sequence identity were
229 carried out using the Silva database (Version 13_08).

230 Genomic DNA extraction was performed using the “Canvax” kit, rt-PCR (with
231 ITS1/ITS4 and rcbLF/rcbLR primers) and purification of the PCR fragments with the
232 “Omega” kit. Quantification was conducted using QUBIT 2.0 equipment and reagents.
233 The sequencing was followed by Sanger Sequencing with the BigDye Terminator v3.1
234 Kit on a Genetic Analyzer (ABI3500 from Applied Biosystems).

235 2.6. Monitoring the microalgal attachment

236 Cell adhesion was measured at the end of the experiments, after 3 months. In the case of
237 the flat-panel PBRs, the surfaces were thoroughly took out from the PBR and rinsed out
238 with sterile Mediterranean seawater to remove foulants and non-adherent cells (Soriano-
239 Jerez et al., 2023). Then, the Chl *a*¹² fluorescence of the adhered microalgae cells was
240 measured to quantify the cell adhesion on each surface (Soriano-Jerez et al., 2021;

¹² Chlorophyll *a*

241 Zeriouh et al., 2017). In the case of the tubular PBR, the tube sections that included the
242 tested surfaces were taken off the closed-PBR and rinsed with sterile Mediterranean
243 seawater. The biofouling formations on each surface were detached using cellular
244 scrapers and washed with 40 g/L ammonium bicarbonate to eliminate salts and
245 weighed.

246 2.7. Analytical procedures

247 To determine the biomass concentration, samples were taken daily from each PBR to
248 spectrophotometrically – this was done using a Helios Omega UV-Vis
249 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) – and to evaluate the photosynthetic
250 capacity of the cells (Fv/Fm) using a PAM chlorophyll fluorometer (PAM-2500
251 chlorophyll fluorometer, Heinz Walz GmbH) (López-Rosales et al., 2014). By dry
252 weight, the absorbance measurements were verified twice a week. The average of the
253 three results from each determination was used. The PBRs were supplemented with
254 distilled water to make up for evaporation losses. The biomass productivity and specific
255 growth rate were determined as described elsewhere (Camacho-Rodríguez et al.,
256 2013a).

257 Phosphate and nitrate concentrations in the supernatants were quantified using the
258 American Public Health Association's 4500-P and 4500-N spectrophotometric methods
259 (APHA, 1995). A bicinchoninic acid protein assay kit (Catalog No BCA1 and B9643,
260 Merck KgaA) was used to quantify the protein concentration. The carbohydrate
261 concentration was measured following the sulfuric acid-UV protocol explained by
262 Albalasmeh et al. (2013).

263 The anion and cation concentrations were determined using the 930 Compact IC Flex
264 System from Metrohm (Herisau, Switzerland) with a conductometric detector and a
265 UV/VIS detector. Separations were carried out using two different chromatographic

266 columns from Metrohm – Metrosep A Supp 7 (250 mm x 4 mm) for anion separation
267 and Metrosep C6 (150 mm x 4 mm) for cation separation. Data acquisition and
268 evaluation of the chromatograms were performed using MagIC Net 3.3 software
269 (Metrohm). The metal concentrations (Li, Mg, P, S, K and Ca) in the biomass and
270 biofouling were measured by ICP-MS (iCAP TQ ICP-MS, ThermoFisher Scientific),
271 after grinding up and digesting 500 mg of lyophilised biomass or biofouling in order to
272 make the cations available for measurement. The metal concentrations in the biofilm
273 were calculated as the difference between the amount present in the biofouling and the
274 biomass.

275 2.8. Statistical analyses

276 A one-way ANOVA¹³ test was used to carry out the significant difference analysis. The
277 effects of the following elements on biofouling formation were performed using
278 multifactor ANOVA: the type of PBR (factor A) and surface (factor B), as determined
279 by the ANCOVA¹⁴; and the influence of the factors and their interaction on the cell
280 adhesion of both microalgae, as established by the covariance analysis (protein and
281 carbohydrate concentrations in the supernatant). The threshold for statistically
282 significant variations in the mean response between the factors was fixed at 5.0%
283 ($p < 0.05$). The means were discriminated using Fisher's LSD¹⁵ at a 95.0% confidence
284 level. The statistical data were analyzed using Statgraphics Centurion XVII (version
285 17.2.04) statistics software (2014, Statpoint Technologies, Inc., Warrenton, VA).
286

¹³ Analysis of variance

¹⁴ Covariance analysis

¹⁵ Least significant difference

287 **3. Results and discussion**

288 3.1. Culture monitoring

Parameter	Culture			
	Flat-panel	Flat-panel	Tubular	Tubular
	<i>C. sorokiniana</i>	<i>N. gaditana</i>	<i>C. sorokiniana</i>	<i>N. gaditana</i>
μ , day ⁻¹	0.15±0.01	0.10±0.01	0.18±0.01	0.12±0.01
D, day ⁻¹	0.10±0.01	0.06±0.01	0.15±0.01	0.10±0.01
Y_{B/NO_3} - batch, g g ⁻¹	1.37±0.10	1.42±0.10	3.10±0.20	3.12±0.20
Y_{B/NO_3} - continuous, g g ⁻¹	1.02±0.07	1.22±0.09	3.63±0.25	3.44±0.20
Y_{B/PO_4} batch, g g ⁻¹	13.71±1.00	7.19±0.50	28.56±2.00	14.98±1.05
Y_{B/PO_4} continuous, g g ⁻¹	10.79±0.80	5.59±0.40	18.10±1.30	9.38±0.70
Pb_{batch} , mg L ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	59.56±3.00	55.21±2.80	111.24±5.60	103.12±5.20
$Pbc_{continuous}$, mg L ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	57.69±2.90	53.89±2.70	91.39±4.60	85.37±4.30

Table 1. Growing parameters obtained on each PBR: growth rate (μ , day⁻¹), dilution rate (D, day⁻¹), biomass yield per gram nitrate in batch mode (Y_{B/NO_3} - batch, g biomass/ g consumed nitrate), biomass yield per gram nitrate in continuous mode (Y_{B/NO_3} - continuous, g biomass/ g consumed nitrate), biomass yield per gram phosphate in batch mode (Y_{B/PO_4} batch, g biomass/ g consumed phosphate), biomass yield per gram phosphate in continuous mode (Y_{B/PO_4} continuous, g biomass/ g consumed phosphate), productivity at the end of the batch mode (Pb_{batch} , mg L⁻¹ day⁻¹), productivity during the continuous mode ($Pbc_{continuous}$, mg L⁻¹ day⁻¹).

289 For the *C. Sorokiniana* PBRs, the stationary state was reached in batch mode after 19
290 days, at which point the continuous mode was established. For the *N. gaditana* flat-
291 panel and tubular PBRs, this state started after 12 and 20 days, respectively. As can be
292 seen in Table 1, the growth rate of *C. Sorokiniana* was higher (0.15 day⁻¹ for the flat-
293 panel PBR and 0.18 day⁻¹ for the tubular PBR) than that of *N. gaditana* (0.10 day⁻¹ for
294 the flat-panel PBR and 0.12 day⁻¹ for the tubular PBR). The highest biomass yield was
295 achieved in the tubular PBRs (3.1 g biomass/ g NO₃⁻ in both tubular PBRs, and 28.6 and
296 15.0 g biomass/ g PO₄⁻³ for *C. sorokiniana* and *N. gaditana*, respectively, in each
297 tubular PBR) due to the high biomass productivity – 111.2 and 103.1 mg L⁻¹ day⁻¹ in
298 batch mode for *C. sorokiniana* and *N. gaditana*, respectively, in the tubular PBRs. In
299 contrast, in the *N. gaditana* flat-panel PBR, a biomass yield of 55.2 mg L⁻¹ day⁻¹ was
300 achieved, compared to 59.6 mg L⁻¹ day⁻¹ in the *C. Sorokiniana* flat-panel PBR. Using a
301 dilution rate of 0.10 day⁻¹ for the *C. Sorokiniana* flat-panel PBR, 0.06 day⁻¹ for the *N.*

302 *gaditana* flat-panel PBR, 0.15 day⁻¹ for the *C. Sorokiniana* tubular PBR and 0.1 day⁻¹
303 for the *N. gaditana* tubular PBR, the productivity in continuous mode dropped to 57.7,
304 53.9, 81.4 and 85.4 mg L⁻¹ day⁻¹, respectively, which for both strains was also higher in
305 the tubular PBRs. The batch productivity of *C. sorokiniana* was similar to the batch
306 productivity obtained by Wolf et al. (2016) (31 mg L⁻¹ day⁻¹ in a 320 L flat-panel PBR
307 and 134 mg L⁻¹ day⁻¹ in a 600 L tubular PBR) during September. In the case of the *N.*
308 *gaditana* flat-panel PBR, the productivity obtained for the same dilution rate was
309 similar to that obtained by San Pedro et al. (2016) (from 50 to 60 mg L⁻¹ day⁻¹).
310 However, in the *N. gaditana* tubular PBR, the productivity achieved in the present study
311 was lower than that obtained by San Pedro et al. (2014) (200 – 300 mg L⁻¹ day⁻¹) at the
312 same dilution rate. De Vree et al. (2015) obtained a productivity of 0.9 g L⁻¹ day⁻¹ for *N.*
313 *gaditana* in a flat-panel PBR and 0.57 g L⁻¹ day⁻¹ in a tubular PBR during July-August.
314 Nevertheless, the optical path in the flat-panel PBR used in the de Vree et al. (2015)
315 studies was 2 cm, and a short optical path results in higher productivities (Camacho-
316 Rodríguez et al., 2014; Janssen et al., 2000; Michels et al., 2014^a). Given that
317 environmental conditions cannot be controlled in outdoor experiments, differences in
318 incident irradiance, temperature of the culture media, or even the long culture period
319 resulting from the longer biofouling formation, could be the reasons why there were
320 different productivities reported among the authors (Camacho-Rodríguez et al., 2014; de
321 Vree et al., 2015; García-Abad et al., 2022; Soriano-Jerez et al., 2021). The Fv/Fm
322 remained quite stable throughout the culture period. For the *C. Sorokiniana* flat-panel
323 PBR, the average value was 0.680±0.021, 0.550 ±0.043 for the *C. Sorokiniana* tubular
324 PBR, 0.578±0.027 for the *N. gaditana* flat-panel PBR, and 0.480±0.038 for the *N.*
325 *gaditana* tubular PBR, indicating that the cells were healthy. However, in the middle
326 hours of the day, the Fv/Fm value decreases to values close to 0.4, especially when the

327 biomass concentration was lower, which indicated that the microalgae cells were
328 stressed due to high irradiance.

329 3.2. Evaluation of carbohydrates and proteins in the supernatant

330 Carbohydrate and protein concentrations evolution in the supernatant can be seen in
331 Figure 1. In general terms, the protein concentration (Figure 1a) decreased over the first
332 days in all the cultures and increased at the end of the batch period. The initial decrease
333 in concentration was most notable in the *C. Sorokiniana* tubular PBR (from 0.018 g/L to
334 0.003 g/L in 5 days) while in the case of the *C. Sorokiniana* flat-panel PBR, it remained
335 constant (at around 0.02 g/L). García-Abad et al. (2022) also observed a decrease in
336 protein concentration during the lag phase and an increase during the exponential phase
337 in *C. reinhardtii* and *I. galbana* cultures. The cells do not synthesize proteins during the
338 lag phase but rather consume them to maintain their metabolism due to the synthesis of
339 EPS, such as polysaccharides and proteins, being a function of the reproduction of
340 microalgal cells and the photosynthetic activity (Li et al., 2016). However, when the
341 continuous phase started, the protein concentration decreased in all the cultures and then
342 remained constant (at around 0.05 g/L for both the *C. Sorokiniana* PBRs, 0.09 g/L for
343 the *N. gaditana* flat-panel PBR and 0.12 g/L for the *N. gaditana* tubular PBR). In the *N.*
344 *gaditana* PBRs, the amount of protein in the supernatant was higher than in the *C.*
345 *sorokiniana* PBRs.

Figure 1. (a) Total protein concentration (g/L) present in the supernatant and (b) total carbohydrate concentration (g/L) present in the supernatant for the culture period in each PBR.

346 On the other hand, the carbohydrate concentration (Figure 1b) increased during the
347 batch period in all the cultures, reaching concentrations of 0.08 g/L, 0.05 g/L, 0.03 g/L
348 and 0.06 g/L in the *C. Sorokiniana* flat-panel, *C. Sorokiniana* tubular, *N. gaditana* flat-
349 panel and *N. gaditana* tubular PBRs, respectively. However, when the continuous state
350 began, the carbohydrate concentration decreased, and then remained constant over time
351 at values of around 0.05 g/L, 0.03 g/L, 0.03 g/L and 0.04 g/L for the *C. Sorokiniana*
352 flat-panel, *C. Sorokiniana* tubular, *N. gaditana* flat-panel and *N. gaditana* tubular PBRs,
353 respectively. This decrease of the carbohydrate concentration during the continuous
354 culture mode could be due to a lower secretion rate of this EPS compared to the dilution
355 rate to which the culture is subjected. That is, the concentration is lower than expected
356 because the culture is diluted with the dilution rate. Alternatively, it could be due to
357 potential adsorption onto the PBR surfaces, thereby becoming incorporated into the
358 biofouling formation. In this case, the highest amount of carbohydrates present in the
359 supernatant was for the *C. sorokiniana* flat-panel PBR.

360 Despite the cultures being outdoors during the summer months and thus subjected to
361 high irradiance, the protein and carbohydrate concentrations present in the cultures was
362 within the normal values for indoor microalgae cultures (García-Abad et al., 2022;
363 Soriano-Jerez et al., 2021; You & Barnett, 2004). As the presence of EPS increases with
364 irradiance (García-Abad et al., 2022; Garza-Rodríguez et al., 2022), it was expected that
365 a higher concentration of them would be found, but their concentration was similar to
366 that found under indoor conditions (García-Abad et al., 2022; You & Barnett, 2004).
367 This might be due to the dark zones formed in the PBRs as a result of the light path
368 length, the light attenuation induced by the self-shading effect of the cells, or even cell
369 adhesion on the inside of the PBR, reducing light availability for the microalgae inside
370 the culture (Acién-Fernández et al., 1998; Michels et al., 2014b; Slegers et al., 2011).

Figure 2. (a) Lithium concentration (ppm), (b) sodium concentration (ppm), (c) potassium concentration (ppm), (d) magnesium concentration (ppm), and (e) calcium concentration (ppm) present in the supernatant for the culture period in each PBR.

373 Figure 2 shows the cation concentrations (Na^+ , K^+ , Li^+ , Mg^{+2} , Ca^{+2}) analysed. The
 374 initial concentration of each cation was the same across all the cultures because the
 375 seawater and culture medium was identical. The tendency for all cations is that their
 376 concentration decreases due to these micronutrients being taken up by the microalgae,
 377 the tendency being greater in the tubular PBRs, as occurred with the macronutrient

378 intake (Table 1). However, there was a marked difference in the concentration of the
379 divalent cations Mg^{+2} and Ca^{+2} between the flat-panel and tubular PBRs. These have a
380 huge influence on biofouling formation (Abrahamse et al., 2008; Geesey et al., 2000;
381 Kilmer et al., 2021). The lowest value was found at the end of the culture in the tubular
382 PBRs. This might be because these cations interact with organic molecules present in
383 the supernatant, such as proteins or carbohydrates, by forming complexes. They then
384 attach to the surface, as is the case with bacterial cell attachment (van de Ven et al.,
385 2008; Wang et al., 2019). It could also explain why the protein and carbohydrate
386 concentrations in the supernatant outdoors were like those in the indoor experiments,
387 since they are no longer found as free molecules, but rather form part of the
388 conditioning film on the PBR surface. Therefore, if one takes into account the
389 possibility of complexes forming, which affect biofouling formation, one would expect
390 cell adhesion to be higher in closed tubular PBRs than in the other PBRs. One should
391 note that there was also a significant decline in Li^{+} and K^{+} in the *N. gaditana* tubular
392 PBR, but no relationship was found between this low concentration during the
393 continuous mode and biofouling formation.
394

Figure 3. (a) Chlorine concentration (ppm), (b) bromine concentration (ppm), and (c) sulphate concentration (ppm) present in the supernatant during the culture period for the different PBRs.

396 There is a general tendency for the anion concentrations (Cl^- , Br^- , SO_4^{2-}) in the
 397 supernatant to decrease due to them being taken up by the microalgae and, as in the case
 398 of the cations, the decrease is greater in the tubular PBRs (Figure 3). Some references
 399 affirms that anions affect protein interactions more than cations do (Medda et al., 2015),
 400 and taking the ‘Hofmeister series’ into consideration, the SO_4^{2-} ion has a huge influence
 401 on promoting protein precipitation in the aqueous solution. Therefore, the lower SO_4^{2-}
 402 concentration at the end of the culture in the tubular PBRs could be due to the higher
 403 intake in these culture systems or because it interacts with organic molecules, which
 404 promote biofouling formation.

405

Figure 4. Concentration of metals (mg/kg) present in the biofilm, calculated as the difference between the concentration in the biofouling and that in the biomass.

407 Figure 4 shows the biofilm metal content of all the PBRs at the end of the culture. The
 408 amounts of metals present in the biofilm formed in the tubular PBRs was greater than
 409 that in the flat-panel PBRs. This was especially the case for magnesium, which reached
 410 concentrations of 14.7 and 15.9 g/ kg in the *N. gaditana* and *C. sorokiniana* tubular
 411 PBRs, respectively, while in the flat-panel PBRs, the concentrations were 9.2 g/kg for
 412 *N. gaditana* and 8.3 g/kg for *C. sorokiniana*. The lithium and sulphur concentrations
 413 were also higher in the tubular PBRs. However, there were no significant variations in
 414 the phosphorus or calcium concentrations between the PBRs, although calcium also
 415 influences cell adhesion (Geesey et al., 2000; Wang et al., 2019). Nevertheless, this
 416 metal (Ca^{+2}) influences microalgae growth and lipid synthesis (Song et al., 2022) so the
 417 decrease in concentration of this cation (detected in Figure 2e) could be caused by the
 418 synthesis of lipids, as well as by complexes forming with the organic molecules. In

419 accordance with San Pedro et al., the fatty-acid content was higher in the tubular PBRs
420 (San Pedro et al., 2014) than in the flat-panel PBRs (San Pedro et al., 2016), which
421 might explain why the calcium uptake was higher in the tubular PBRs than in the flat-
422 panels. Potassium was not detected in the biofilm since it was only present in the cells.
423 Comparing the results in Figures 2 and 3 with the results in Figure 4, one can confirm
424 that the decrease in the ion concentrations, such as the magnesium, lithium and sulphate
425 present in the supernatant, was because they became part of the biofilm. This was
426 especially pronounced in the tubular PBRs, possibly due to their interaction with the
427 proteins and other organic molecules present in the culture, leading to biofouling
428 formation in these tubular PBRs being greater than in the flat-panel one (Abrahamse et
429 al., 2008; Geesey et al., 2000; Kilmer et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2019).

430 3.5. Physicochemical characterization of microalgal lawns and the tested surfaces

Microalga	PBR	Place	Contact angles, °			Interaction components and surface properties, mJ/m ²							
			θ_w	θ_F	θ_D	γ_s^{LW}	γ_s^+	γ_s^-	γ_s^{AB}	ΔG_{coh}	γ_s	τ_0	γ_c
<i>C. sorokiniana</i>	Flat-panel	Culture	30.6±7.0	41.9±3.8	55.0±3.2	31.5	0.4	57.3	9.9	42.5	41.4	62.6	45.4
<i>N. gaditana</i>	Flat-panel	Culture	47.5± 6.3	42.4±3.1	72.0±5.8	21.8	4.0	33.2	23.0	8.7	44.8	49.2	41.6
<i>C. sorokiniana</i>	Tubular	Culture	9.0±5.1	16.4±4.2	37.3±6.3	41.0	0.8	56.9	13.1	35.7	54.1	71.9	48.0
<i>N. gaditana</i>	Tubular	Culture	14.0±6.4	16.6±2.5	48.8±4.0	34.9	1.9	54.1	20.5	30.6	55.5	70.8	47.7
<i>C. sorokiniana</i>	Flat-panel	Biofouling	12.4±5.0	20.8±4.0	25.1±2.4	46.1	0.1	58.0	5.4	39.3	51.5	71.1	47.8
<i>N. gaditana</i>	Flat-panel	Biofouling	19.3±5.2	21.0±3.3	32.9±4.0	43.0	0.4	53.2	9.5	32.4	52.5	68.7	47.1
<i>C. sorokiniana</i>	Tubular	Biofouling	21.0±5.3	25.0±9.8	34.4±9.3	42.3	0.3	54.2	8.3	34.7	50.6	68.0	46.9
<i>N. gaditana</i>	Tubular	Biofouling	47.5±6.7	36.0±9.2	45.2±9.7	38.0	0.8	29.9	10.0	2.5	47.9	49.2	41.6

Table 2. Results for the contact angles, surface interaction force components, cohesion free energy, free energy, water adhesion tension and critical surface tension for culture lawn of *N. gaditana* and *C. sorokiniana* after 3 months in a flat-panel and tubular PBRs and a lawn of biofouling formed in them. (θ_w) contact angle between the surface and the polar solvent 1 (water); (θ_F) contact angle between the surface and polar solvent 2 (formamide); (θ_D) contact angle between the surface and the apolar solvent (diiodomethane); (γ_s^{LW}) (the interaction component related to the Lifhitz-van der Waals forces; (γ_s^+) the electron-accepting component ; (γ_s^-) the electron-donating component; (γ_s^{AB}) the acid-base component; (ΔG_{coh}) the cohesion free energy variation; (γ_s) the surface free energy; (τ_0) the water adhesion tension; and (γ_c) the critical surface tension. Results are presented as the average \pm SD (n = 3). A surface is considered smooth for Ra values below 0.6 μ m (Zerrouh et al., 2017).

432 Table 2 shows the contact angle, surface energy components ($\gamma_s^{LW}, \gamma_s^+, \gamma_s^-, \gamma_s^{AB}$), free
433 energy of cohesion (ΔG_{coh}), surface free energy (γ_s), water adhesion tension (τ_0) and
434 critical surface tension (γ_c) of the *C. sorokiniana* and *N. gaditana* lawns. These were
435 obtained from the suspension of culture cells and the cells from the biofouling formed
436 in each PBR after 3 months. The *N. gaditana* culture from the flat-panel lawn presented
437 similar contact angle values as those reported by Zerriouh et al. (2017) for the same
438 microalgae at the stationary state in the batch culture while the tubular lawn presented a
439 more hydrophilic character. However, the *N. gaditana* lawn, elaborated with cells from
440 the biofouling after 3 months of culture, showed that the adhered cells in the flat-panel
441 PBR were more hydrophilic than the culture cells ($\tau_0 = 49.2 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ for non-adhered
442 cells and 68.7 mJ/m^2 for adhered cells), whereas the adhered cells in the tubular PBR (τ_0
443 $= 49.2 \text{ mJ/m}^2$) were less hydrophilic than the culture cells ($\tau_0 = 70.8 \text{ mJ/m}^2$). The *C.*
444 *sorokiniana* culture lawn showed this microalga to be more hydrophilic than *N.*
445 *gaditana* (the *C. Sorokianiana* τ_0 was higher than the *N. gaditana* τ_0) and, for this strain,
446 the hydrophilic character is also greater in the tubular PBR than in the flat-panel PBR.
447 As in the case of *N. gaditana*, the *C. sorokiniana* biofouling lawn showed that attached
448 cells ($\tau_0 = 71.1 \text{ mJ/m}^2$) were more hydrophilic than the microalgae cells in suspension
449 ($\tau_0 = 62.6 \text{ mJ/m}^2$) in the flat-panel PBR whereas in the tubular PBR the adhered cells (τ_0
450 $= 68 \text{ mJ/m}^2$) were less hydrophilic than the non-adhered cells ($\tau_0 = 71.9 \text{ mJ/m}^2$). This
451 difference in the degree of hydrophilicity between the two PBRs for the same strain
452 could be due to a morphological change or to the surface composition because of
453 varying light and nutrient availability resulting from different degrees of mixing in each
454 PBR and because of the surface/volume ratio. The variation between adhered and non-
455 adhered cells could be due to a morphological change in the adhered microalgae cells
456 while they are part of the biofilm matrix. As both microalgae have hydrophilic surfaces,

457 they should tend to adhere to hydrophobic surface (Zeriouh et al., 2017). Therefore, the
458 highest cell adhesion should take place on TRC premium DH® ($\tau_0 = -1.8 \text{ mJ/m}^2$, see
459 Table 3) plastic bag walls and PDMS coated on the walls. However, Hempasil X3®,
460 which is an amphiphilic coating with a surface chemistry reorganisation in contact with
461 water droplet, with an hydrophobic character presented very low *N. gaditana* cell
462 adhesion (Soriano-Jerez et al., 2021, 2023) so the general tendency could not be applied
463 in this case. Moreover, this supposition cannot be applied to an additive-based surface,
464 such as the PEG/PDMS coating, given its amphiphilic character and surface
465 reorganization in contact with water.

Microalga	Coating	Ra (μm)	Contact angles, $^\circ$			Interaction components and surface properties, mJ/m^2							
			θ_w	θ_F	θ_D	γ_s^{LW}	γ_s^+	γ_s^-	γ_s^{AB}	ΔG_{coh}	γ_s	τ_0	γ_c
None	Pristine	0.08 \pm 0.02	91.4 \pm 4.4	77.0 \pm 4.0	55.1 \pm 5.3	31.4	0.2	5.4	2.2	-51.8	33.5	-1.8	31.4
	TRC												
	premium												
	DH $^\circ$												
<i>C. sorokiniana</i>	DBE-311	71.5 \pm 14.0	62.8 \pm 13.6	58.5 \pm 14.7	29.4	0.1	17.1	2.8	-18.4	32.3	23.1	29.4	
	PDMS	87.3 \pm 14.0	60.2 \pm 9.2	63.2 \pm 11.1	26.7	2.1	1.7	3.8	-54.3	3.5	3.4	26.7	
	Hempasil	44.6 \pm 18.8	43.4 \pm 18.0	36.5 \pm 9.6	41.3	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	40.2	0.7	19.6	42.0	51.8	42.4	
	X3 $^\circ$												
	TRC												
premium	60.7 \pm 14.0	45.0 \pm 12.6	39.0 \pm 15.1	40.1	0.3	18.9	4.7	-18.3	44.8	35.7	37.8		
DH $^\circ$													
<i>N. gaditana</i>	DBE-311	89.8 \pm 17.5	74.5 \pm 12.8	65.9 \pm 4.7	25.2	0.1	5.2	1.4	-52.6	26.6	0.3	25.2	
	PDMS	64.8 \pm 16.3	51.5 \pm 14.6	58.0 \pm 8.5	29.8	1.1	17.4	8.8	-15.3	38.6	31.0	36.5	
	Hempasil	86.7 \pm 19.2	76.1 \pm 11.8	51.2 \pm 6.0	33.6	0.6	9.2	4.6	-37.2	38.2	4.3	33.6	
	X3 $^\circ$												
	TRC												
premium	42.9 \pm 11.7	25.7 \pm 9.5	36.7 \pm 9.6	41.3	1.1	30.0	11.7	0.7	53.0	53.3	42.8		
DH $^\circ$													

Table 3. Results for the contact angles, surface interaction force components, cohesion energy, free energy, water adhesion tension and critical surface tension for coatings immersed 3 months in a *C. sorokiniana* and *N. gaditana* culture. (θ_w) contact angle between the surface and the polar solvent 1 (water); (θ_F) contact angle between the surface and polar solvent 2 (formamide); (θ_D) contact angle between the surface and the apolar solvent (diiodomethane); (γ_s^{LW}) (the interaction component related to the Lifhitz-van der Waals forces); (γ_s^+) the electron-accepting component ; (γ_s^-) the electron-donating component; (γ_s^{AB}) the acid-base component; (ΔG_{coh}) the cohesion free energy variation; (γ_s) the surface free energy; (τ_0) the water adhesion tension; and (γ_c) the critical surface tension. Results are presented as the average \pm SD (n = 3). A surface is considered smooth for Ra values below 0.6 μm (Zeriouh et al., 2017).

467 Table 3 shows the characterization of the pristine plastic bag (TRC premium DH®) and
468 of each surface immersed in *C. sorokiniana* and *N. gaditana* culture for 3 months in
469 flat-panel PBRs. The tubular PBR surfaces could not be analysed because the coatings
470 broke when attempting to detach them from the PBR. The characterizations for the
471 clean PEG/PDMS coating, PDMS and Hempasil X3® can be seen in a previous
472 publication (data not published). The plastic bag used for the PBR, TRC premium
473 DH®, is considered a purely hydrophobic surface ($\tau_0 < 0 \text{ mJ/m}^2$). However, after 3
474 months of immersion in the *C. sorokiniana* and *N. gaditana* cultures, it became
475 hydrophilic ($\tau_0 > 30 \text{ mJ/m}^2$), especially in the *N. gaditana* culture. In the case of the
476 PDMS coating, something similar happened, it went from being a very hydrophobic
477 surface to a hydrophilic surface in the *N. gaditana* culture whereas, in the *C.*
478 *sorokiniana* culture, although the hydrophilicity increased, it remained a hydrophobic
479 surface. In contrast, the coating prepared with 4% of DBE-311 copolymer went from
480 being a very hydrophilic surface when it was clean to a hydrophobic surface after 3
481 months of immersion in both cases, although especially in the *N. gaditana* culture.
482 While Hempasil X3® went from being a hydrophobic surface to a very hydrophilic
483 surface after 3 months immersed in the *C. sorokiniana* culture, it remained hydrophobic
484 after 3 months immersed in the *N. gaditana* culture. This change in the materials'
485 surface properties after 3 months of immersion does not follow an obvious pattern. One
486 would expect the surfaces to become more hydrophilic since both microalgae are
487 hydrophilic (see Table 2). However, this only occurred with TRC premium DH® and
488 PDMS. The increase in hydrophobicity of the Hempasil X3® and DBE-311 coatings
489 may be due to the adhesion of exopolymeric substances or complexes, which favour
490 biofouling formation over time (García-Abad et al., 2022; Soriano-Jerez et al., 2021). It
491 is worth mentioning that, in the case of the DBE-311 coating, this increase in

492 hydrophobicity might also be due to additive loss, given that it was subjected to high
 493 temperatures and irradiance (Camós-Noguer et al., 2016; Camós Noguer et al., 2017).
 494 The decrease in the additive content, which provides its hydrophilic character, means
 495 that the coating could end up as a hydrophobic PDMS surface, which would no longer
 496 have antibiofouling properties.

497 3.6. Cell adhesion on different surfaces

Figure 5. (a) Cell adhesion (cells/mm²) on each surface immersed for 3 months in flat-panel PBRs and (b) cell adhesion (mg/mm²) on each surface immersed for 3 months in tubular PBRs; (c) photos of each surface after 3 months immersion in flat-panel PBRs; and (d) photos of each surface after 3 months immersion in tubular PBRs.

498 Figure 5 shows the cell adhesion on each surface after 3 months of immersion in
 499 cultures of the marine microalgae *N. gaditana* and *C. sorokiniana* in flat-panel and
 500 tubular PBRs. Figure 5a shows that, in the flat-panel PBRs, cell adhesion on the
 501 PEG/PDMS prepared with DBE-311 copolymer was lower than on the PDMS (92% for
 502 *N. gaditana* and 70% for *C. sorokiniana*) and TRC premium DH[®] (95% for *N.*
 503 *gaditana* and 65% for *C. sorokiniana*) controls for both strains. In the tubular PBRs,
 504 microalgae cell adhesion was much higher than in the flat-panel PBRs for all surfaces
 505 (see Figure 5b), even for the coating prepared with DBE-311 copolymer. Consequently,
 506 the biofouling formation had to be quantified as adhered biomass per area instead of by
 507 the number of cells. This difference in cell adhesion may be due to the light availability
 508 inside the PBRs. As the tubular PBR has a short light path and a very long solar

509 collector, there is high irradiance inside it as well as a greater temperature gradient,
510 which favour cell adhesion (García-Abad et al., 2022; San Pedro et al., 2016).
511 Conversely, in the flat-panel PBR, there is a higher light path and fluid dynamics due to
512 its geometry, meaning it has more dark zones (de Vree et al., 2015); therefore, the cells
513 are less stressed, which can result in less adhesion. Even so, the DBE-311 additive-
514 based surface reduced biofouling formation by 65% for *N. gaditana* and 69% for *C.*
515 *sorokiniana* compared with the PDMS surface control, and by 74% for *N. gaditana* and
516 62% for *C. sorokiniana* compared with the TRC premium DH® control. Despite the
517 cell adhesion in our study not being as low for the coating prepared with the DBE-311
518 additive as in experiments carried out indoors over 8 months with the microalga *N.*
519 *gaditana* (Soriano-Jerez et al., 2023), it was possible to reduce cell adhesion
520 substantially. Therefore, coatings based on hydrogel technology continue to exhibit
521 their biofouling-reducing capabilities even when scaled up to pilot plant proportions
522 However, this decrease in antibiofouling effectiveness might stem from the loss of
523 additives from the coating due to the significant temperature fluctuations (the culture is
524 around 25°C while outdoors the temperature exceeds 40°C at midday) and the high
525 irradiance to which it is subjected, which can favour additive release (Camós Noguier et
526 al., 2017).
527 Considering the results shown in Figure 5, one can see that the surface has a statistically
528 significant influence on cell adhesion (p-value < 0.05). In this case, 3 homogeneous
529 groups were found among the surfaces tested in each PBR: the group with less adhesion
530 comprising Hempasil X3®, followed by the group comprising the coating prepared with
531 the DBE-311 additive, and the last group, which presented the greatest adhesion after 3
532 months of culture immersion, made up of PDMS and TRC premium DH® in the flat-
533 panel PBRs, and PDMS and PMMA in the tubular PBRs. Therefore, even though the

534 PDMS/PEG coating prepared with the DBE-311 additive did not prevent biofouling
 535 formation by 100%, it did reduce cell adhesion compared to traditional PBR materials
 536 by 62 - 95 % (depending on the microalgae and the type of PBR). Hence, it would
 537 appear to be a good alternative for obtaining a more efficient microalgae culture system,
 538 at least if employed for 3 months or less, even outdoors in the most adverse weather
 539 conditions.

Factors	p-Value	F-Factor	Influence percentage, %
Covariates			
Protein in supernatant	0.0000	66.28	10.73
Carbohydrates in supernatant	0.0037	11.09	1.80
Main effect			
A: PBR type	0.0000	207.33	33.57
B: Surface	0.0000	166.77	27.00
Interactions			
AB	0.0000	166.17	26.90

Table 4. Influence of the type and surface of PBR tested and the EPS substances (proteins and carbohydrates) in *N. gaditana* cell adhesion on surfaces, according to the covariance analysis.

540 Tables 4 and 5 show the statistical data analysis for biofouling formation after 3 months,
 541 detailing the influence (in percentages) of each variable on *N. gaditana* and *C.*
 542 *sorokiniana*, respectively. The type of PBR is the factor which had the highest influence
 543 on *N. gaditana* cell adhesion, up to 33.57%, followed by the surface in contact with the
 544 culture (the material or coating), at 27% (Table 4). The interaction of both factors
 545 together also had a huge influence (26.9%). The type of PBR influenced the fluid
 546 dynamics and light availability, both of which affected biofouling formation (de Vree et
 547 al., 2015; Kichouh-Aiadi et al., 2021), while the influence of the PBR's surface on cell
 548 adhesion due to its surface properties and cell-surface interactions remains unknown
 549 (García-Abad et al., 2022; Soriano-Jerez et al., 2021; Zerriouh et al., 2017). Regarding
 550 the covariates selected, the protein concentration in the supernatant presented the
 551 highest percentage influence (10.73%). This is supported by previous research where it

552 was observed that the higher the protein concentration present in the supernatant, the
 553 greater the cell adhesion (García-Abad et al., 2022; Soriano-Jerez et al., 2021); this is
 554 due to the key role played by this EPS on conditioning film formation.

Factors	p-Value	F-Factor	Influence percentage, %
Covariates			
Protein in supernatant	0.0008	15.99	3.94
Carbohydrates in supernatant	0.3060	1.11	0.27
Main effect			
A: PBR type	0.0001	27.29	6.72
B: Surface	0.0000	181.14	44.61
Interactions			
AB	0.0000	180.55	44.46

Table 5. Influence of the type and surface of PBR tested and the EPS substances (proteins and carbohydrates) in *Chlorella sorokiniana* cell adhesion on surfaces, according to the covariance analysis.

563 In the case of *C. sorokiniana* (Table 5), the PBR surface was the factor which had the
 564 greatest influence on cell adhesion (44.61%). Even though the type of PBR also had an
 565 influence (6.72%), it was lower than for *N. gaditana*. This could be because *C.*
 566 *sorokiniana* resists high temperature, being highly productive even at 35°C (Romero
 567 Villegas et al., 2021). Therefore, regardless of high temperature gradients, this did not
 568 cause greater stress in the tubular PBR than in the flat-panel PBR, perhaps also
 569 explaining why there was no difference in the protein concentration in the supernatant
 570 in both PBRs (Figure 1). The protein concentration also influenced biofouling formation
 571 (3.94%), but for this microalga, the carbohydrate concentration did not (p-value > 0.05).

572 3.7. Microbiota community diversity in the tubular PBR

Figure 6. (a) Taxonomic classification of the bacterial communities at the phylum level, (b) at the class level, and (c) at the order level. (d) Taxonomic classification of the eukaryotic communities at the phylum level, (e) at the class level, and (f) at the order level.

573 Due to the high adhesion produced in the tubular PBR (Figure 5), an evaluation of the
 574 diversity of the microbiota community, such as bacteria and eukaryotes (Figure 6), was
 575 carried out using illumine sequencing. The microbiota community present in the *C.*
 576 *sorokiniana* tubular culture revealed that 99.96% represented eukaryote diversity while
 577 the rest, 0.042%, comprised a bacterial community. The phylogenetic variation was

578 studied while the tubular PBR culture was in stationary state. These results were
579 consistent with previous research that shown that in some instances, microalgae can
580 represent up to 95% of the microalgal biomass produced in outdoors and long-lasting
581 PBR cultures (Molina-Grima et al., 2022; San Pedro et al., 2016). The culture samples
582 were successfully classified into their phylum, class, and order. If considering only taxa
583 with a relative abundance of more than 1%, the overall bacterial community consisted
584 mainly of 6 phyla, 7 classes, and 10 orders. Figure 6 presents the phylogenetic
585 classification of the phylum, class, and order found in the bacterial community.
586 *Acidobacteriota* were the most significant phylum at 35.7%, followed by
587 *Pseudomonadota*, with a relative abundance of 28.6%, the two major bacteria found in
588 marine environments (Cottrell & Kirchman, 2000; Sánchez Zurano et al., 2020).
589 Sánchez-Zurano et al. (2020) reported that this bacterial community is associated with
590 the degradation of dissolved organic matter and particles derived from phytoplankton
591 (Buchan et al., 2014). *Actinomycetota* were the next most abundant phylum, at 14.3%,
592 followed by *Bacillota*, with *Chloroflexota* and *Nitrospirota* having a relative content of
593 7.1%. On the other hand, *Acidobacteriota*, dominated the bacterial class classification
594 with a relative abundance of 35.7%, followed by *Alphaproteobacteria* (21.4%) and
595 *Actinomycetota*. This is in accordance with Sánchez-Zurano et al. (2020). At the order
596 level, the three most abundant were DA023 (21.4%), *Rhizobiales* and *Actinobacteridae*
597 (both at 14.3%). It should be noted that the *Rhizobiales* are common contaminants of
598 cultures such as *Scenedesmus sp.*, *Chlorella vulgaris* or *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*,
599 and they can also act as algal growth promoters (Sánchez Zurano et al., 2020). Referring
600 to the eukaryotic communities overall, they mainly comprised 3 phyla, 3 classes and 5
601 orders. The majority of the phylum is 99.76% in *Viridiplantae*, 99.75% in the case of
602 class for *Chlorophyta* and for the order 99.7 *Trebouxiophyceae*, is a class of unicellular

603 chlorophyte green algae, the most recognised genus of which is *Chlorella*. This was
604 identified with primers to be *Chlorella sorokiniana*, as described in the Materials and
605 Methods section. The other PBRs were also analysed. In the case of the *C. sorokiniana*
606 flat-panel PBR, the result of the analysis shows sequence similarities of 100% for *C.*
607 *sorokiniana*, and in the case of the *N. gaditana* PBRs, the similarities were higher than
608 99% for *N. gaditana*. Therefore, the greater biofouling formation in *C. sorokiniana*
609 tubular PBR could be due to the greater amount of bacteria present in the culture
610 (Giraldo et al., 2019).

611 **4. Conclusions**

612 Although the PEG/PDMS-based coating prepared with DBE-311 did not completely
613 prevent biofouling formation, it significantly reduced cell adhesion in *N. gaditana* and
614 *C. sorokiniana* outdoor cultures during the summer, under culture conditions that are
615 prone to biofouling formation, such as a high EPS and ion concentration. In the *C.*
616 *sorokiniana* tubular PBR, where the cell adhesion was significantly higher, possibly due
617 to the greater bacteria amount present, the coating prepared with DBE-311 reduced
618 biofouling formation by 61% compared to the PMMA subsequently with the biomass
619 productivity increasing. Thereupon, the removal of metals by bioremediation will be
620 greater. Therefore, this coating proved to be a good alternative to traditional materials
621 when constructing efficient closed-PBR outdoors at the pilot-plant scale.

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